

Psychological features of students' professional identity

K.A. Bizhanova

Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Department of Pedagogy and Educational Management, Kazakhstan.

B.A. Arinova

Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Department of Pedagogy and Educational Management, Kazakhstan.

K.Sh. Moldassan

Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Department of Pedagogy and Educational Management, Kazakhstan.

M.D. Murzagulova

L.Gumilyov Eurasian National University, faculty of Social Sciences, department of Pedagogy.

A.M.Tekesbayeva

Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Department of Pedagogy and Educational Management, Kazakhstan.

ABSTRACT: Statement of the problem of identity, determination of the conditions for its formation in various life contexts are urgent tasks due to the identity crisis of modern person noted by researchers (G.M. Andreeva, 2015; T.M. Buyakas, 2020; M.V. Zakovorotnaya, 1999; L. M. Putilova, 2019; L.B. Shneider, 2022, etc.), the urgent need to provide psychological assistance in resolving this crisis. Years of social, political, and economic instability in Kazakhstan have led to the erosion of guidelines necessary for both personal and professional self-determination; as a result, the problem of finding one's own identity is extremely important for a modern young person, and the task of studying the psychological conditions that ensure the process of achieving identity, arises most acutely. In this article, the authors study the relationship between identification and the motivational structure of life values of first-year students. The dependence of the feeling of belonging to a study group, the level and degree of identification of a student in the areas of profession, education, family, social life and hobbies are explored. The main results of the analysis of relationships are presented depending on the predominance of humanistic or pragmatic orientation in the study group. Gender motivational features of the studied relationships are discussed.

Key words. Identification, Motivation, Structure of Life Values, Interactions.

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1. Introduction

The formation of personal identity is the central psychological new formation of adolescence; it is in adolescence that this the process proceeds most intensively. The experience of identity is updated both in the personal and professional spheres of human

life. The problem of identity arises in terms of the implementation of a person's life and professional ideology, in terms of implementing the professional training of a specialist, in terms of becoming a professional. The process of identity formation continues throughout life, being a factor in the psychological well-being, life satisfaction and personal growth of every person in a modern, rapidly changing world.

In the context of the above, the most relevant seems to be the study of the formation of personal and professional identity in adolescence, when, within the framework of leading, educational and professional activities, cognitive and professional interests are formed, life and professional plans are formed, the problem of choosing a profession and obtaining vocational education is solved, as well as during early adulthood, at the stage of beginning professional activity, positioning oneself in the world of adults.

Modern conditions of rapid social change place special demands on the personality of students as future specialists. While studying at a university, there is a collision between the desired future in professional self-realization and the real present (one's abilities, professionally important qualities and skills). Experiencing disappointment in one's profession, dissatisfaction with certain academic disciplines, doubts about the correctness of one's professional choice, and a loss of interest in studies lead to a correction of professional intentions, which is impossible without building an ideal image of the "I" in the profession, identifying with this ideal and reducing the discrepancy with it.

To revise and correct a professional choice, a student needs to use the identification mechanism as the subject's identification (unification) with another individual or group based on their real/desired personal or social similarity with inclusion in their inner world and acceptance of norms, values, patterns of behavior, social role expectations and responsibilities.

It is identification at the decisive stages of professional development that helps the student make the formed ideas about himself as a future specialist more adequate with the help of timely changes made to the professional "I-concept".

2. Literature Review

We should note that scientific publications contain a wide range of works devoted to the study of identification. Many authors emphasize that identification characterizes the psychological basis of conscious behavior (G. M. Andreeva, N. JI. Ivanova, N. M. Lebedeva, T. G. Stefanenko, JI. B. Schneider, V. A. Yadov, D. Abrams, M. Hogg, N. Tajfel).

The problem of identity is studied as one of the key points in the psychology of social cognition (G. M. Andreeva, E. P. Belinskaya, A. Tashfel, J. Turner, D. Abram, M. Hogg, M. Augustinos, I. Walker, N. Elmer, R. Brown, P. Oaks, etc.), ethnic, cross-cultural and social psychology of interaction (N. M. Lebedeva, Yu. P. Platonov, Z. V. Sikevich, G. U. Soldatova, T. G. Stefanenko, V. A. Tishkov, V. Yu Khotinets), developmental psychology (I. A. Snezhkova, X. Rodriguez-Tome, J. A. Marcia) . In the course of the research, questions about the structure, types, models and features of identification are discussed.

Professional identity is discussed in psychology as a “complex integrative psychological phenomenon”, as “the leading characteristic of a person’s professional development, which indicates the degree of acceptance of the chosen professional activity as a means of self-realization and development” as awareness of one’s identity with the group and assessment of the significance of membership in it, etc.

Unlike gender, ethnic and other types of identity, professional identity requires special, purposeful, socially organized preparation and is performed for a certain reward. “Special purposeful training organized by society” also means training in higher educational institutions with the aim of obtaining a specific specialty. The process of studying at a university is accompanied, according to many researchers, by the formation of professional identity. But scientists do not separate the concepts of “professional identity of a specialist” and “professional identity of a student,” considering them as a common psychological phenomenon, but only among representatives of different groups (students and working people). We consider the professional identity of a student and the professional identity of a specialist as two different psychological phenomena that have a continuous nature. Many researchers emphasize that professional identity is a product of long-term personal and professional development, which appears at fairly high levels of mastery of a profession. For example, E. P. Ermolaeva notes that professional identity develops when a subject achieves a high level of professional skill and acts as a stable coordination of the basic elements of the professional process.

In light of this, the results of numerous studies on professional identity and conducted on students look ambiguous. Thus, the professional identity of a student and the professional identity of a specialist are different psychological phenomena that require separate consideration.

L. B. Schneider points out that most researchers interpret identity as the result of a certain process (self-knowledge, self-understanding, identification, identification-alienation, etc.). In line with this interpretation, we understand the professional identity of students as the result of the subject’s purposeful activity within the framework of educational and professional activities, characterizing the significance of the profession for the student as a means of satisfying his needs. A student’s professional identity is the unity of self-image, emotional experiences and conscious activity associated with acquiring a profession, on the basis of which a sense of identity with oneself as a future specialist appears. The system of ideas about oneself within the framework of a student’s professional identity contains ideas about oneself as a future specialist (belonging to a certain professional group), about one’s professional and educational-professional goals, and about one’s capabilities to realize these goals.

In accordance with the above data, we assume that it is possible to identify and describe the psychological features of students’ professional identity.

3. Methodology

Research Design

This paper uses the following research methods:

In order to identify the main psychological features of students' professional identity, we conducted a theoretical and experimental study of this issue. The experimental study itself was carried out from October 2023 to March 2024 on the basis of the Al-Farabi Kazakh national university (Almaty, Kazakhstan). 206 students of the Faculty of Philosophy and Political Science from the first to the fourth year took part in it. The following methods were used in the experimental study:

- personal professional plan (E. A. Klimov adapted by L. B. Schneider)
- student professional identity questionnaire (author's development)
- Who am I? (T. McPartland - M. Kuhn)
- Motivation for vocational training (V. G. Katashev)
- Test of life-meaning orientations (SLO) (D. A. Leontyev)
- Identification research (B. Long, R. Ziller, R. Henderson)
- to study reflexivity (A. V. Karpov)
- diagnostics of the level of empathic abilities (V.V. Boyko)
- value orientations (M. Rokeach)
- for professional reflection.

The results were processed using SPSS program.

4. Findings/Results

The research specifies the following basic concepts of the study:

Based on the methodology of E. A. Klimova and L. B. Shneider "Personal professional plan", all subjects were divided according to levels of professional identity: low (13% of respondents), average (57% of respondents) and high (30% of respondents).

Analysis of the results using the author's methodology "Questionnaire for Professional Identity of Students" showed that 64% of students with a low level of professional identity development (compared to 6% of students with a high level) are characterized by either the manifestation of negative emotions in relation to their future profession, or the manifestation of passivity, or both of them combined. At the same time, 37% of subjects with a high level of professional identity development (compared to 8% of students with a low level) are characterized by either positive emotions towards their future profession, or an active attitude towards it, or both combined.

Indicators reflecting the personal component of professional identity, which was studied using the methods of A. V. Karpov "Study of Reflexivity" and V. V. Boyko "Diagnostics of the Level of Empathic Abilities," state its significance. Of the subjects at a low level of development of pro-identity, 51% have a low level of development of reflexivity and 33% have a low level of development of empathic abilities, while of the subjects at a high level of development of pro-identity, 78% have an average and high level of reflexivity and 86% have an average and high level of development of empathic abilities.

The motivational component of professional identity was studied using the methodology of V. G. Katashev "Motivation for Professional Training". It was revealed that the level of motivation for professional learning is different among psychology students at different levels of professional identity development. Among respondents with a low level of profitability development, only 5% of students are highly motivated for professional learning, while among respondents with average and high levels of profitability development – 53% and 42%, respectively.

Analyzing the indicators of the value-semantic component of professional identity ("Test of life-meaning orientations" by D. A. Leontyev), we can say that an average and high level of meaningfulness in life favors the development of a high level of professional identity of a student - a future psychologist (96% of students with a high level of development of pro-identity have an average and high level of meaningfulness in life). The most significant values-goals, which were studied using M. Rokeach's "Value Orientations" method, for all students are: love - spiritual and physical intimacy with a loved one (average rank in the sample - 5.04), physical and mental health (average rank according to the sample – 5.4), having good and loyal friends (average rank according to the sample – 6.63). In our opinion, these are significant universal values that characterize the broad social group "students". Commitment to these values covers the differences between groups based on the professional identity of students.

Data on the mechanisms of professional identity development, obtained using the methodology of B. Long, R. Ziller, R. Henderson "Identification Research", and according to the task for professional reflection, indicate that groups of students with different levels of professional identity development are significantly different from each other by identification with the samples: "practical psychologist" (significance level 0.002), "psychologist profession" (significance level 0.0001), "psychologist" (significance level 0.02), "student - future psychologist" (significance level 0.019). Thus, the updated processes of professional identification are significantly related to the level of development of students' professional identity. The same can be said about the mechanism of professional reflection. Of all students with an activated mechanism of professional reflection, 6% have a low level of professional identity development, 46% and 48% have an average and high level of professional identity development

5. Discussion

Based on the obtained data from quantitative and qualitative processing of the results, we identified the psychological characteristics of students' professional identity described below.

1. The professional identity of students is of an activity nature. The professional identity of students develops as a result of educational and professional activities and contributes to the successful acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities for further professional activities. Professional identity can develop in the conditions of specially organized classes through activities in which the subject of targeted activity is the development of components, characteristics and mechanisms of students' professional identity

2. The professional identity of students is probabilistic in nature. Despite the fact that the university creates the same conditions for the development of professional identity for all students, by the 4th year 38% of graduates acquire a high level, and 18% - a low level of development of students' professional identity. Some students plan to work in their specialty after graduating from a higher education institution, the rest prefer other professions not related to the specialty obtained at the university.

3. Students' professional identity develops unevenly.

Latent and crisis periods alternate in development; stages with an evolutionary and revolutionary course can be distinguished.

Yu. P. Povarenkov notes that "the leading sign of uneven professional development is professional macro- and microcrises." The study of the professional development of students at a pedagogical university allowed this author to identify two main crises – the second and fourth years.

Our research at the Faculty of Philosophy and Political Science showed that each course is characterized by certain crisis phenomena. So, in the first year, the crisis begins after the first session and can be characterized as emotional. Comparing the results obtained in the first and second semester, we can conclude that there was a decrease in the positive emotions of first-year students regarding the profession and everything connected with it (at a significance level of 0.01)

Compared to the rest, the second year looks the most prosperous, but starting from the third year, crisis manifestations begin to intensify, increase every year and reach their critical levels in the fourth year. By the fourth year, many indicators reflecting the student's professional identity sharply decline. By analyzing the results obtained, we can diagnose a severe mental state and strong emotional experiences of graduates.

The professional identity crisis of graduates is characterized by a decrease in positive emotions regarding the profession. This is due to the fact that, in their opinion, the profession does not satisfy all life needs. 70% of graduates think so. Due to changing needs (for example, first-year students do not yet think about how their profession can support them financially, but for fifth-year students this is already very important), satisfaction with their future profession has also changed. 24% of graduate students have no desire to work in their specialty (compared to 5% in the first year). The statement "If I were again in a situation of choice, I would no longer choose this area of professional activity" was answered positively by 18% of graduates (compared to 5% of first-year students). The

overall indicator of students' professional identity also decreased significantly from the first to the fourth year.

4. The next psychological feature of students' professional identity is that it has an individual character of development. Despite the identified periods of crisis, each has its own pace and course of development. This depends on the personal qualities of students (including their compliance with the requirements of the profession), on readiness (intellectual, motivational, psychophysiological, etc.) for studying at a university, on the social environment (negative attitude towards the acquired profession or support from parents and friends), etc. The development of professional identity of students has different motivational bases and the degree of their expression.

5. Gender characteristics can be traced in the development of professional identity. In particular, the construction of correlation galaxies showed that among male representatives the relationships between the components of professional identity of students are more pronounced ($r = 0.4-0.6$ at a significance level of 0.01) and form a clear structure that is limited to professional identification, while while for girls, the components of a student's professional identity are weakly interconnected ($r = 0.2-0.3$) and form a vague structure. Although if we compare the absolute indicators for all methods, the results of girls are superior to the results of young people in all cases.

Based on the results of correlation and factor analysis of the results of the "Student Professional Identity Questionnaire" method, we designated these bipolar factors as "Emotions from satisfaction/dissatisfaction of a person's needs in a given profession" and "Position of the student's active/passive attitude towards the acquired profession."

The first factor is "Emotions from satisfaction/dissatisfaction of a person's needs in a given profession" (scale "Emotional attitude"). A person has a set of certain conscious or unconscious needs (physiological, material, spiritual, social, etc.). By choosing a certain profession, a person hopes to satisfy his existing needs. When a student begins to study, becoming more familiar with the true content of the profession, he has a clearer idea of how this profession can satisfy his needs and how suitable he is for this profession. The prerequisite for any activity is one or another need; accordingly, the prerequisite for the educational and professional activities of students are those needs that are planned to be satisfied in future professional activities. Therefore, we can assert that the professional identity of students directly depends on the satisfaction/dissatisfaction of the needs that caused their educational and professional activities and the accompanying emotions.

The second factor is "The position of the student's active/passive attitude towards the acquired profession" (Scale "Conscious activity"). The position of a student's conscious active attitude towards the acquired profession can also be designated as the position of a "subject". The importance of this position of the student in obtaining a quality education has been discussed more than once. As the main prerequisite for successful mastery of a profession, many authors consider "not so much specific knowledge and skills and not so much psycho physiological characteristics that could be useful in the chosen profession, but... a subjective attitude towards one's actions and actions"

Depending on the results, all subjects can be placed at the intersection of two factors and nine types of professional identity of students can be identified. The distribution of subjects by type of professional student identity is presented in the table.

According to the Kruskal-Wallis H criterion, these types differ from each other at a significant level (up to 0.0001) in the parameters identified by the methods used.

We suggest the following psychological characteristics of students with different types of professional identity:

Table No. 1: distribution of students by types of professional identity

"Conscious activity" scale	"Emotional attitude" scale		
	predominantly negative emotions	no clear predominance	mostly positive emotions
low level	Type 1 6%	Type 2 6 %	Type 3 0%
average level	Type 4 6%	Type 5 57%	Type 6 8%
high level	Type 7 0%	Type 8 10%	Type 9 7%

Type 1 is characterized by a passive position, accompanied by negative emotions regarding the future profession. Students belonging to this type believe that this profession is not for them, it is not able to satisfy their needs, and they will not be able to realize themselves in it. There is a passive attitude towards the acquired profession, there are negative emotions regarding the profession and everything connected with it. Most likely, there was disappointment in the profession.

Type 2 is characterized by a passive position, accompanied by neutral emotions regarding the future profession. The predominance of a passive attitude towards the acquired profession. Students of this type are confident that their university education will be enough for them to further work, but they do not make specific plans for what they will do after graduation. The predominance of emotions in relation to the acquired profession depends on various situations.

Type 3 is characterized by a passive position, accompanied by positive emotions regarding the future profession. Students belonging to this type have predominantly positive emotions towards their future profession; they have a desire to spend most of their time doing things related to the profession, but despite this, there is a passive attitude towards the acquired profession. Most likely, these students can be classified as "dreamers."

Type 4 is characterized by a moderately expressed active position, accompanied by negative emotions regarding the future profession. Students belonging to this type have negative emotions regarding this profession and everything connected with it, since they believe that the profession of a psychologist does not satisfy all of their life needs and demands. But these students can approach different educational and professional situations differently: in some cases they actively set goals and carry out their plans, and in others they let everything take its course.

Type 5 is characterized by a moderately expressed active position, accompanied by neutral emotions regarding the future profession. Students of this type do not have any pronounced tendencies; their indicators are at an average level. This suggests that a student may approach different educational and professional situations differently; the predominance of emotions also depends on different situations. Potentially, students of this type, under certain circumstances, can move to any other type.

Type 6 is characterized by a moderately expressed active position, accompanied by positive emotions regarding the future profession. The professional identity of students of this type is predominantly active and expressed. These students consider the profession of psychologist to be their calling, one of the ways of self-realization in life. The thought that they will work in their specialty makes them happy; there is a desire to spend most of the time doing things related to the profession. Conscious activity in relation to the future profession is at an average level.

Type 7 is characterized by an active position, accompanied by negative emotions regarding the future profession. Despite the fact that students belonging to this type have negative emotions regarding this profession and everything connected with it, they strive to achieve certain goals in this profession and show significant activity in educational and professional activities. It can be assumed that there are some external incentives for their activity, in addition to the content of the future profession itself (social obligations, parental opinion, etc.).

Type 8 is characterized by an active position, accompanied by neutral emotions regarding the future profession. Students of this type do not have strong positive emotions (they vary depending on the situation), but they do have a position of an active attitude towards the acquired profession, which can also be designated as the position of a "subject". Students who take an active position in relation to the acquired profession set themselves goals in the professional sphere and strive to achieve them, plan their lives in line with the profession, know how to obtain the information they are interested in, and additionally read specialized magazines and books.

Type 9 is characterized by an active position, accompanied by positive emotions regarding the future profession. The student's professional identity is pronounced and active. Students who adhere to this position believe that the profession of a psychologist satisfies their needs and demands; in it they see their calling and a way of self-realization. They calculate their future so that they can work as a psychologist, set goals and achieve them. At every opportunity they try to gain experience in practical psychological activities; read additional psychological literature.

The sixth and eighth types of professional identity of students are similar in their high results using various methods, i.e. students belonging to these two types use different identification strategies (based on emotions or conscious activity), but in the end both of them turn out to be highly professionally identified students.

In our opinion, one of the important conditions for the development of a student's professional identity is the constant activation of such mechanisms of personal development as identification and reflection. Identification and reflection as mechanisms of

self-knowledge are indicated. Maralov points that identification with oneself acts as one of the most powerful mechanisms of self-knowledge... reflection makes it possible to “look” at the whole process as if from the outside” and also acts as a mechanism of self-knowledge

We understand identification as the process of identifying oneself with a significant person, image, or social group on the basis of a positive emotional connection. In our opinion, identification with significant people in a given profession is one of the most powerful mechanisms for the development of professional identity at student age. It is at the university that young men and women become acquainted with representatives of this profession, especially within the framework of courses related to the history of the development of science.

The results of the identification process, even under the condition of emotional acceptance of the material and, as a consequence, the emergence of a desire among students to be more active, to work more on themselves, to set high goals and achieve them, may not have the proper impact on the development of the subject position and remain with students at the level of memories and emotions.

To prevent this from happening, the following mechanism for developing a student's professional identity is necessary – reflection. Reflection is the process of self-knowledge by the subject of internal mental acts and states, “going beyond the limits of any directly, automatically current process or state.”

One of the main psychological features of a student's professional identity, according to our opinion, is that it can be activated through special developmental activities.

The total duration of the formative experiment was 36 hours (4 months). The experimental and control groups were represented by 18 and 22 students. Before the start of the formative experiment, the groups had indicators that were not significantly different from each other (the significance level of the differences according to the Mann–Whitney U test was greater than 0.76).

The experiment was based on the hypothesis that increasing the professional identity of students is possible through the activation of the mechanisms of professional identity and through the targeted activity of students in relation to the components of professional identity. The group process of developmental practical classes included the following types of methodological tools, techniques and tasks: role-playing games, analysis of professional situations, reflective analysis, thematic discussions and debates, tasks for self-knowledge, self-development and self-forecasting, exercises for the development of identification and reflection, autogenic and relaxation techniques and etc.

Analysis of the results of the study of the level of development of professional identity of students in the experimental and control groups, obtained after conducting the formative experiment, made it possible to judge the fairly high effectiveness of the developmental classes conducted. In order to statistically compare the indicators measured in two different conditions on the same sample of subjects, the Wilcoxon T-test was used. It allows you to establish not only the direction of changes, but also their severity.

The analysis shows that during the developmental practical classes, the students of the experimental group began to more consciously plan their future in psychology, correlate the requirements of the profession and their capabilities, and clearly see the ways of preparing for the realization of their professional goals. Almost everyone who did not connect their future with psychology changed their minds and identified themselves as future practical psychologists. Students began to evaluate their lives as productive and meaningful (the level of significance of positive changes according to the Wilcoxon T-criterion is less than 0.03).

At the same time (under the influence of some uncontrolled variables) negative changes occurred in the control group. Professional identity and professional reflection have decreased significantly. More students, compared to the first section, stopped planning their lives in line with psychology, and the emotions received from meeting the needs of the profession decreased. Identification with the model of a "practical psychologist" has weakened (the level of significance of negative shifts in Wilcoxon T-test less than 0.04).

This can be explained by the fact that the time of the second control cut fell at the beginning of the summer session. Therefore, it can be assumed that students who did not participate in developmental practical classes showed signs of an emotional "pre-session" crisis. And those students who participated in developmental practical classes not only improved their professional identity indicators, but were also able to successfully cope with this crisis.

In addition, an analysis of correlation galaxies was carried out (according to the Pearson r criterion) before and after the formative experiment in groups in order to diagnose qualitative changes. From the analysis of correlation galaxies, we can conclude that the relationships in the control group remained virtually unchanged. At the same time, in the experimental group, the professional identity of students became interconnected with the meaning of life ($r = 0.645$, $p < 0.01$). The direction and meaningfulness of life in general began to correlate with the professional future ($r = 0.591$, $p < 0.05$). In the experimental group, goals in life and goals regarding the future profession ceased to exist separately from each other (experimental group $r = 0.609$, $p < 0.01$; control group $r = 0.209$, $p > 0.05$). The professional identity of students from the experimental group began to correlate with the idea of themselves as a strong personality with sufficient freedom of choice to build their lives in accordance with their goals and ideas, that life is in their hands and they manage it ($r = 0.657$, $p < 0.01$).

Thus, we can conclude that a comprehensive program aimed at developing the professional identity of students influenced the level of development of students' professional identity, the students' awareness of planning their future in the profession, the adequacy of the relationship between the requirements of the profession and their capabilities, and the ability to clearly see the paths of preparation to the realization of your professional goals. In addition, there have been qualitative changes in the structure of relationships between students' professional identity. The psychological phenomenon being studied has become more interconnected with the meaningfulness of life in general, with life goals, with the idea of oneself as a strong personality and with the processes of professional identification.

6. Limitations

Research into the process of identity formation shows the ambiguity and uneven dynamics of this process, which accompanies overcoming psychosocial crises and solving personally significant problems. In today's complex and uncertain world, there is an increasingly close interaction between different types of identity, and, as a consequence, the instability of the entire systems of ideas about oneself when external, social parameters change.

7. Conclusion

1. Professional identity of students is an independent psychological phenomenon.
2. The professional identity of students has its own psychological characteristics: activity-based, probabilistic, uneven and individual development.
3. We can also highlight gender characteristics, the possibility of development through mechanisms of identification and reflection in the process of special developmental activities.
4. The study identified the main characteristics of a student's professional identity: "Emotions from satisfaction/dissatisfaction of a person's needs in a given profession" and "The position of the student's active/passive attitude towards the acquired profession."
5. Through the implementation of a special program, you can effectively influence the development of a student's professional identity.

Also identified features of student identification with his study group, which may be useful for organizing educational work at the university. Preliminary diagnostics before the start of training will make it possible to predict the specifics of the adaptation processes of individual students and, in general, the nature of relationships in the group. For students with a predominant pragmatic orientation, the importance of career guidance increases, since awareness of the benefits and advantages of mastering a future profession will allow interests to be transferred from the sphere of hobbies to the sphere of education and profession. The results obtained show the need for purposefully creating a favorable psychological atmosphere and stimulating the manifestation of friendliness in the study group, for example, with the help of specially organized work of a psychologist at a university.

For further discussions we suggest research on the possibility of using artificial intelligence to automatically identify students based on their behavior and activity patterns,

Examine the effectiveness of various student identification methods in various educational settings and environments, such as online courses or seminars.

Analysis of the influence of students' professional identification on their learning and performance. Research on the possibility of using identification data to personalize the educational process.

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